

SILICA-EPOXY INTERFACES IN BICONTINUOUS NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In classic discontinuous silica-epoxy nanocomposites, strong matrix-reinforcement interactions may enhance toughness by introducing new energy absorption mechanisms. These silica-epoxy interactions are mediated either directly through inherent silica silanol groups or *via* tethering of reactive amine or epoxide groups. Recently, bicontinuous silica-epoxy nanocomposites have been formed by backfilling monolithic silica aerogel with epoxy resin. The continuous reinforcement network provides long-range load transfer, inherently uniform silica distribution, and synergistic interlocking effects. When preparing these nanocomposites, the silica aerogel is typically hydrophobised to prevent moisture absorption which can lead to shrinkage or cracking prior to backfilling. However, the aggressive reagents used (typically trimethylchlorosilane, TMCS) give almost complete conversion of silanol groups, leading to an inert surface which forms only very weak interactions with epoxy resin. Under shear loading, this poor interface leads to brittle failure at relatively low strain. Mild hydrophobisation agents such as dimethyldimethoxysilane (DMDMS), instead give incomplete conversion of silanols to yield a “part-methylated” surface which, while providing some hydrophobic character, forms a stronger silica-epoxy interface. Furthermore, as it does not form acidic byproducts, which would otherwise catalyse ring opening, DMDMS may be used alongside (3-glycidyloxypropyl)trimethoxysilane (GPTMS) to give a “part methylated + epoxidated” surface. Across a broad range of silica aerogel densities, both surface types give significantly lower moisture content (“part methylated” \approx 2.6 wt.%, “part methylated + epoxidated” \approx 1.4 wt.%) when compared with unmodified silica aerogel (\approx 9.8 wt.%). These values are greater than those of TMCS-methylated silica aerogel, however, in contrast to unmodified silica aerogel, uncracked monoliths are formed in all cases.

1 INTRODUCTION

For unidirectional carbon fibre composites (UD CFRPs), conventional polymer matrices provide insufficient shear support against fibre micro-buckling in compression. Consequently, the compressive strength of UD CFRPs is typically less than 60% of their tensile strength. Commercial nanosilica reinforcements improve matrix shear strength and modulus leading to enhanced fibre composite compressive strength [1]. These nanocomposite matrices typically contain dispersed discontinuous nanofillers with no direct load transfer within the reinforcement phase. Furthermore, above very modest loadings (6 SiO_x vol.%) nanofiller agglomeration leads to decreased compressive performance in unidirectional fibre composites. Bicontinuous nanocomposites feature a macroscopically continuous reinforcement which interlocks with the matrix phase to give synergistic mechanical property enhancement [2]. Silica-epoxy bicontinuous nanocomposites have been formed with loadings of up to 10 SiO_x vol.% by backfilling a continuous silica reinforcement (silica aerogel) with epoxy resin [3]. These novel materials display distinct super-linear power law loading-property relationships owing to fractal branching of the silica network. In contrast, the equivalent trends for discontinuous nanocomposites are distinctly linear or sub-linear [4-6]. At present, modulus enhancement in silica-epoxy bicontinuous nanocomposites is curtailed by low reinforcement loadings and a weak matrix-reinforcement interface. To aid aerogel processing (decreased network shrinkage and moisture absorption), reinforcement networks were previously formed with fully-methylated surfaces. However, this functionalisation precludes covalent bonding at the matrix-reinforcement interface. In particulate systems, specimens with inert interfaces have significantly worse strength, stiffness and toughness *vs.* otherwise-equivalent specimens with covalently-bound interfaces [7]. Commercial discontinuous nanosilica reinforcements feature reactive surface silanol groups for improved toughness through strong covalent bonding with the epoxy resin matrix [8, 9]. Here, novel part-methylated silica aerogel surface chemistries are developed to balance the processing benefits of methylation with the superior mechanical properties of reactive surfaces. Two new surface types are introduced: “part-methylated” and “part-methylated + epoxidated” (Figure 1). The former features reactive silanol groups while the latter has silanols and additional tethered epoxide groups. Both surfaces were partially methylated with dimethyldimethoxysilane (DMDMS), a mild methylating agent. Unlike trimethylchlorosilane (TMCS) – a classic methylating agent for silica aerogel, DMDMS produces no acidic byproducts and is therefore well-suited for co-functionalisation in the presence of acid-sensitive epoxide groups. Synthesis of the silica skeleton is described in [10]. To confirm compatibility with a range of silica content, the tetramethylorthosilicate (TMOS) volume fraction in the sol-gel precursor was varied for measurement of aerogel physical properties relevant to epoxy backfilling.

Figure 1. Chemical structures of silica aerogel surfaces discussed in this paper.

2 SURFACE MODIFICATION METHODS

Part-methylated and part-methylated + epoxidated silica aerogel monoliths were formed by functionalisation of TMOS-derived wet silica gel monoliths. Cylindrical monoliths ($d = 6$ mm, $l = 15$ mm) were prepared by stirring the appropriate mixture of TMOS, water and ethanol (TMOS volume fraction, $\phi_{\text{TMOS}} = 0.23$) for 3 h at 25 °C before transfer of the liquid sol to high density polyethylene moulds [3]. After gelation, samples were aged in the supernatant for 4 days at room temperature to consolidate the silica network through increased inter-particle crosslinking. After demoulding, samples were transferred to ethanol prior to functionalisation. After functionalisation, samples were exchanged first into ethanol and then acetone before drying. Samples were dried from supercritical CO₂ to minimise the capillary forces that drive pore collapse and overall sample shrinkage. Infra-red spectroscopy was used to identify surface-bound groups. All IR spectra are normalised to the transmittance of the largest Si-O-Si (siloxane) signal (1050 cm⁻¹ – 1080 cm⁻¹) at an arbitrary transmittance (T) value of $T = 64.2$. This signal has been chosen as it represents the bulk amorphous silica (SiO_x) only and hence will not change as a result of new siloxane linkages formed during surface modification [11]. Consequently, by

using the same feedstock aerogel, intensities of all other relevant signals may be compared semi-quantitatively between candidate surfaces to contrast relative loadings of various surface groups.

Table 1. IR signals relevant to the functionalisation of silica aerogel surfaces [11].

Bond	Si-O-H	Si-C-H	Si-O-Si	Si-O-C-H	Epoxide
	3300 – 3500 (<i>O-H stretch</i>)	2975 (<i>C-H stretch</i>)	1080 (<i>stretch</i>)	2855 (<i>C-H stretch</i>)	910 (<i>asymm. Stretch</i>)
Wavenumber [cm ⁻¹]	950 (<i>Si-O stretch</i>)	1250 (<i>Si-C-H bend</i>)	800 (<i>bend</i>)		
		840 (<i>Si-C stretch</i>)	455 (<i>rocking</i>)		
		755 (<i>Si-C stretch</i>)			

To achieve a part-methylated + epoxidated surface, a simultaneous functionalisation reaction was trialled using the mild methylating agent DMDMS. This reagent replaces TMCS which was found to catalyse epoxide ring opening by releasing HCl during grafting [12]. Functionalisation solutions were prepared by first, separately hydrolysing GPTMS and DMDMS (1 mol.dm⁻³) in an ethanol-water mixture ($n_{\text{water}}/n_{\text{silane}} = 1.33$). Solutions were then combined in various volume ratios to vary the relative silane concentrations. The mole fraction of GPTMS out of the total number of moles of silane (χ_{GPTMS}) is used when discussing the effect of functionalisation solution on aerogel properties. Functionalisation was performed by immersing wet silica gel monoliths in functionalisation solution for 48 h at 65 °C. 50 mL of functionalisation solution was used for every 4 mL of wet silica gel. Samples were then exchanged to acetone *via* ethanol and dried by critical point drying (CPD). Relative intensity (decreased transmittance) of the 910 cm⁻¹ (epoxide) signal increases with increasing χ_{GPTMS} (Figure 2 (a)). This relative intensity is quantified as the difference in transmittance between the Si-alkyl (850 cm⁻¹) and epoxide (910 cm⁻¹) signals ($\Delta T_{850 \text{ cm}^{-1} - 910 \text{ cm}^{-1}}$) (b)). A greater value of $\Delta T_{850 \text{ cm}^{-1} - 910 \text{ cm}^{-1}}$ indicates a greater degree of GPTMS grafting relative to methylating agent (DMDMS) grafting. The systematic change in relative intensity of these two signals with functionalisation solution composition shows that both 3-(glycidyloxypropyl)silyl (GPS) and dimethylsilyl (DMS) residues are bound to the surface. A constant ratio would indicate that only GPS residues were bound. $\Delta T_{850 \text{ cm}^{-1} - 910 \text{ cm}^{-1}}$ increases sharply with GPTMS content before levelling off. This gradient decrease commences between $\chi_{\text{GPTMS}} = 6 \text{ mol.}\%$ and $\chi_{\text{GPTMS}} = 13 \text{ mol.}\%$. DMDMS should bind to the surface more rapidly than GPTMS due to its smaller steric bulk. At $\chi_{\text{GPTMS}} = 38 \text{ mol.}\%$ $\Delta T_{850 \text{ cm}^{-1} - 910 \text{ cm}^{-1}}$ approaches the value seen for the $\chi_{\text{GPTMS}} = 100 \text{ mol.}\%$ sample, hence, in this range of GPTMS content, GPS residues dominate the grafting. This dominance may result from the ability of a single GPS residue to prevent binding of DMDMS at a relatively large number of neighbouring silanol sites due to the large steric bulk (relatively large radius of gyration) of its longer chain. The trend in specimen shrinkage with χ_{GPTMS} approximately follow the $\Delta T_{850 \text{ cm}^{-1} - 910 \text{ cm}^{-1}}$ trend (Figure 2 (b)). Uncracked monoliths were formed with functionalisation solutions containing up to and including $\chi_{\text{GPTMS}} = 21 \text{ mol.}\%$ (Figure 2 (c)). Beyond this value, the capillary pressures associated with moisture absorption caused specimen disintegration. The $\chi_{\text{GPTMS}} = 6 \text{ mol.}\%$ functionalisation solution composition was selected for further study due to its relatively high $\Delta T_{850 \text{ cm}^{-1} - 910 \text{ cm}^{-1}}$ and relatively low shrinkage. Silica aerogel formed with a DMDMS-only functionalisation solution is also a suitable candidate reinforcement as it produces uncracked “part-methylated” monoliths bearing reactive silanol groups.

(c)

Figure 2. (a) Overlaid IR spectra for silica aerogel monoliths formed after treatment with functionalisation solutions containing varying ratios of DMDMS and GPTMS. (b) Volume shrinkage and difference in transmittance ($\Delta T_{850\text{ cm}^{-1} - 910\text{ cm}^{-1}}$) between IR signals at 850 cm⁻¹ and 910 cm⁻¹ plotted against χ_{GPTMS} for silica aerogel monoliths formed after treatment with functionalisation solutions containing varying ratios of DMDMS and GPTMS. (c) Silica aerogel monoliths formed after treatment with functionalisation solutions containing varying ratios of DMDMS and GPTMS. From left to right: χ_{GPTMS} = 0 mol.%, χ_{GPTMS} = 3 mol.%, χ_{GPTMS} = 6 mol.%, χ_{GPTMS} = 13 mol.%, χ_{GPTMS} = 21 mol.%, χ_{GPTMS} = 38 mol.%, χ_{GPTMS} = 100 mol.%. For (b) bars show one standard error.

3 PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF FUNCTIONALISED AEROGEL

This section investigates the application of part-methylated and part-methylated + epoxidated functionalised surfaces to silica aerogel of varying silica content and provides a detailed discussion of physical properties. Silica content was controlled by varying sol-gel precursor TMOS volume fraction (ϕ_{TMOS}) in the range of $0.15 > \phi_{\text{TMOS}} > 0.41$. For each ϕ_{TMOS} value, four surface types (methylated, unmodified, part-methylated, and part-methylated + epoxidated) were prepared from a single batch of monolithic wet silica gel. Therefore, prior to functionalisation, the primary structure should be identical for each surface type at a given ϕ_{TMOS} . Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) is used to quantify the moisture content of these mildly-hydrophilic aerogels to determine how this content varies between

different surface functionality and pore characteristics. This moisture content is also used to renormalise mass-dependent properties to the actual silica aerogel mass after moisture removal. Mass loss from silica aerogel is also given by renormalisation of the mass loss at 150 °C, which is the temperature at which removal of physisorbed water is observed to be complete. However, these TGA data give only a semi-quantitative measure of the quantity of surface-bound groups for two reasons: Firstly, the Si atoms of surface-bound residue remain bound to the silica surface as Si-O bonds are not broken in this temperature range and consequently only the organic components are removed (as methane or methanol in the case of TMS or DMS residues) [13]. Secondly, above 200 °C silanol groups will undergo condensation to form new siloxane linkages resulting in loss of water which increases the overall mass loss. Consequently, TGA dry mass loss values are compared only in terms of their relative magnitudes for each surface type at a given ϕ_{TMS} [14]. The various samples synthesised for this study are identified by their ϕ_{TMS} and surface type (Figure 1). Surface-bound groups are identified by the following names: TMS (from TMCS), silanol (Si-OH), methoxy (residual methoxy groups in unmodified silica aerogel), DMS (from DMDMS), and GPS (from GPTMS). The structures of these surface-bound groups are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Chemical structures of surface-bound groups. TMS = trimethylsilyl, DMS = dimethylsilyl, GPS = (3-glycidyloxypropyl)silyl.

Density and porosity

Envelope densities were measured by mass and volume measurement due to the incompatibility of hydrophilic porous materials with Archimedes' density measurement in water. However, due to the high precision of the balance and callipers used, repeat measurement yielded low uncertainties. For each surface type, envelope density generally increases with increasing ϕ_{TMS} . Methylated aerogel shows a reasonably-linear envelope density trend and is a good match for the TMOS-water aerogel reported previously [3]. The trends for the other three surfaces are far less linear and are shifted to higher densities relative to the methylated surface due to greater volume shrinkage (Figure 4 (b)). Although the shrinkage of the unmodified aerogel (at any ϕ_{TMS}) is greater than that of the part methylated + epoxidated aerogel, the unmodified aerogel has the lower envelope density. This difference is due to the significantly greater relative surface-bound mass fraction of the part-methylated + epoxidated aerogel due to the large

molecular mass of the GPS chains. The skeletal densities of methylated silica aerogel agree with TMOS-water aerogel reported previously for $\varphi_{\text{TMOS}} > 0.2$ [3]. These skeletal densities are significantly lower than the density of amorphous silica (2.3 g.cm^{-3}) due to the contribution of the low-density TMS surface coating [15]. However, at lower values of φ_{TMOS} , the skeletal density increases sharply. This increase is indicative of a lower contribution of the low density TMS surface to the overall skeletal density. This lower contribution results from the decreased specific surface area of the particles due to the significantly slower gelation kinetics at lower [TMOS] (lower φ_{TMOS}) which leads to a smaller TMS volume fraction. From literature, the surface loading of these alkoxy groups is approximately 3.5 nm^{-2} [14, 16]. Skeletal densities of unmodified silica aerogel are an excellent match for literature values for neutral unmodified TMOS aerogel ($1.8 \text{ g.cm}^{-3} - 1.9 \text{ g.cm}^{-3}$) [17]. Despite the lack of intentional surface modification, this skeletal density is still lower than the density of amorphous silica (2.3 g.cm^{-3}) due to the presence of residual surface alkoxy groups resulting from incomplete precursor hydrolysis. From literature, alkoxy surface loading is approximately 2.4 nm^{-2} [14]. In surface-modified silica aerogels, these methoxy groups are displaced during grafting reactions. The skeletal densities of part-methylated, and part-methylated + epoxidated silica aerogel are intermediate between the unmodified and methylated silica aerogels. These relative skeletal densities imply that the surface-bound loading of these samples fall between the surface-bound loadings of unmodified and methylated aerogel. The greater molar volume of the GPS residues vs. DMS residues cancels out their greater mass leading to no net change in skeletal density vs. the part-methylated surface (Figure 4 (c)).

Figure 4 (a) Envelope density (Archimedes method), (b) volume shrinkage, (c) skeletal density (AccuPyc), (d) porosity (calculated from envelope and skeletal densities), (e) water content (TGA), and (f) Mass loss (TGA) of dry silica aerogel monoliths with various surface types plotted against aerogel precursor TMOS volume fraction. Bars show one standard error.

Thermogravimetric analysis

The water content of aerogel monoliths was measured by TGA (Figure 4 (e)). This water content is calculated from the mass loss at the first TGA first derivative minimum. This minimum occurs in the range of 100 °C – 150 °C. Water content is lowest (≈ 0.5 wt.%) for methylated specimens and highest for unmodified specimens (≈ 9.8 wt.%) reflecting their respective superhydrophobicity and hydrophilicity (Figure 5). Accordingly, the water content of the part-methylated aerogel is intermediate of these values (≈ 2.6 wt.%). Interestingly, the water content of part-methylated + epoxidated aerogels is consistently around half that of their part-methylated counterparts (≈ 1.4 wt.%). Decreased water absorbance indicates that binding of GPS residues has a net hydrophobising effect on the aerogel surface which is likely due to the replacement of three highly hydrophilic silanol groups with a single less hydrophilic epoxide group during tripodal binding of GPS. This finding helps justify the choice of GPTMS over hydrophilic (3-aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES) as a linking group. This water content is similar to that reported for GPTMS-functionalised particulate nanosilica (0.7 wt.% – 1.1 wt.%) [18]. Methylated specimens formed from precursors with $\varphi_{\text{TMS}} = 0.15$ to $\varphi_{\text{TMS}} = 0.33$ have similar TGA first derivative profiles with a large mass loss event centred at 360 °C which overlaps with a secondary mass loss event centred at 480 °C (Figure 5 (a)). Decomposition of silica-bound TMS residues is known to produce methane and methanol by methyl displacement in this temperature range [13]. For $\varphi_{\text{TMS}} = 0.41$, the positions of maxima are shifted slightly. However, most organic decomposition still occurs in the range of 300 °C – 600 °C. For $\varphi_{\text{TMS}} = 0.33$ and $\varphi_{\text{TMS}} = 0.41$ a third mass loss event is seen at 730 °C. $\varphi_{\text{TMS}} = 0.17$ is the only sample which has an additional mass loss event at 640 °C. These higher temperature decomposition events are the result of Si-C homolysis. It is not understood why these further events are only seen for these three specimens. The mass loss at 200 °C is due to condensation of surface silanol groups and the resulting water loss. This condensation is most significant for higher φ_{TMS} values where the lower porosity likely generates a greater number of silanol groups inaccessible to TMS modification which are, therefore, available for condensation prior to TMS decomposition [12]. Unmodified specimens begin to lose additional mass immediately after drying (≈ 150 °C) (Figure 5 (b)). This mass loss is due to condensation of the large concentration of silanol groups. A second, broad peak in the TGA first derivative commences at 400 °C due to loss of surface-bound methoxy groups through a hydrolysis mechanism facilitated by moisture generated from silanol condensation. A similar mass loss profile is seen in literature for unmodified TMOS-derived silica aerogel specimens [19]. The TGA first derivative profile of part-methylated silica shows several distinguishable overlapping signals (Figure 5 (c)). Decomposition of dry aerogel again commences at a lower temperature than observed for methylated silica aerogel (≈ 200 °C vs. 350 °C) due to silanol condensation. Loss of methane and methanol follow at higher temperatures as seen for methylated aerogel. The TGA first derivative profiles of $\varphi_{\text{TMS}} = 0.33$, and $\varphi_{\text{TMS}} = 0.41$ differ from the other samples in the form of a smoother broad peak ($\varphi_{\text{TMS}} = 0.33$ and $\varphi_{\text{TMS}} = 0.41$) which again replicates the behaviour seen for methylated silica aerogel. This broader peak may result from a greater degree of mass loss through silanol condensation resulting from a lower degree of surface functionalisation due to a greater proportion of very small pores in the higher density aerogel. The sharp signal seen for $\varphi_{\text{TMS}} = 0.20$ at 650 °C may be due to contamination. The TGA first derivative profile of part-methylated + epoxidated silica aerogel is more like that of methylated silica aerogel than the other surfaces with both showing a large maximum at approximately 350 °C (Figure 5 (d)). The distinct shoulder preceding this peak (starting at 150 °C) may be due to significant loss of condensation products (water) resulting from the self-polymerisation of surface-bound epoxide (GPS residues) in addition to the previously described silanol condensation. Again, $\varphi_{\text{TMS}} = 0.33$ and $\varphi_{\text{TMS}} = 0.41$ show a smoother peak likely due to greater surface silanol concentrations.

Figure 5. TGA data for (a) methylated, (b) unmodified, (c) part-methylated, and (d) part-methylated + epoxidated silica aerogel monoliths with various TMOS volume fractions (ϕ_{TMOS}).

CONCLUSIONS

Two new silica aerogel surface types were synthesised and characterised: part-methylated, and part-methylated + epoxidated. These surfaces enable the formation of moisture-stable, high-density, silica aerogel monoliths with amphiphilic reactive interfaces. The simultaneous independent binding of dimethylsilyl (DMS) and (3-glycidyloxypropyl)silyl (GPS) residues in part-methylated + epoxidated silica aerogel has been confirmed by IR analysis. This bi-functionalisation forms silica aerogel with a surface featuring DMS, GPS and silanol groups. The GPS and silanol groups act as reactive sites and DMS groups provide hydrophobic character for decreased moisture uptake. The shrinkage of part-methylated + epoxidated silica aerogel monoliths was found to decrease with increased proportion of DMS binding relative to GPS binding. A suitable GPTMS/DMDMS ratio ($\chi_{\text{GPTMS}} = 6$ mol.%) was chosen to trade-off shrinkage against GPS loading. Part-methylated and part-methylated + epoxidated surfaces were found to be mildly hydrophilic by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). However, moisture uptake was far less than that of the equivalent unmodified silica aerogel. These reinforcement networks are therefore suitable for backfilling with epoxy resin to form bicontinuous nanocomposites, which may themselves be applied as nanostructured matrices for fibre-reinforced composites.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Jumahat, C. Soutis, F.R. Jones, A. Hodzic. Improved Compressive Properties of a Unidirectional CFRP Laminate Using Nanosilica Particles. *Advanced Composites Letters*. 2010;**19**(6): pp. 204-7.
- [2] D.R. Clarke. Interpenetrating Phase Composites. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*. 1992;**75**(4): pp. 739-58.
- [3] C.M.D. Shaw, D.B. Anthony, I. Hamerton, M.S.P. Shaffer. Bicontinuous silica-epoxy nanocomposites by aerogel infusion. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. 2024;**182**: pp. 108164.
- [4] A. Jumahat, C. Soutis, F.R. Jones, A. Hodzic. Effect of silica nanoparticles on compressive properties of an epoxy polymer. *Journal of Materials Science*. 2010;**45**(21): pp. 5973-83.
- [5] D. Tzetzis, G. Mansour. Nanoindentation, compression and fractural characterization of highly dispersed epoxy silica nanocomposites. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*. 2016;**35**(7): pp. 541-55.
- [6] Bernt Brønmo Johnsen, Marie Bourgeaux-Goget, T. Olsen. Material properties of silica/epoxy nanocomposites. Norwegian Defence Research Establishment (FFI); 2015.
- [7] T. Nazir, A. Afzal, H.M. Siddiqi, S. Saeed, M. Dumon. The influence of temperature and interface strength on the microstructure and performance of sol-gel silica-epoxy nanocomposites. *Polymer Bulletin*. 2011;**67**(8): pp. 1539-51.
- [8] Adam J, Roscher C, Eger C, Adebahr T, Wiczorreck R, Pyrlik M. Evonik Hanse GmbH. Silicon Dioxide Dispersion. Patent: US9376544B2. 28/06/2016.
- [9] S. Sprenger. Nanosilica-Toughened Epoxy Resins. *Polymers*. 2020;**12**(8): pp. 1777.
- [10] C.M.D. Shaw, D.B. Anthony, I. Hamerton, M.S. Shaffer. Bicontinuous Silica-Epoxy Nanocomposites. In *proceedings of: 23rd International Conference on Composite Materials Belfast. 2023*.
- [11] B. Arkles, G. Larson. Silicon Compounds: Silanes & Silicones. Morrisville, PA: Gelest Inc.; 2013.
- [12] C. Shaw. Bicontinuous Silica-Epoxy Matrices for Fibre-Reinforced Composites. London: Imperial College London; 2025.

- [13] Y.W. Ngeow, A.V. Chapman, J.Y.Y. Heng, D.R. Williams, S. Mathys, C.D. Hull. Characterization of silica modified with silanes by using thermogravimetric analysis combined with infrared detection. *Rubber Chemistry and Technology*. 2018;**92**(2): pp. 237-62.
- [14] Z. Li, S. Zhao, M.M. Koebel, W.J. Malfait. Silica aerogels with tailored chemical functionality. *Materials & Design*. 2020;**193**: pp. 108833.
- [15] S. Brunauer, D. Kanro, C. Weise. The surface energies of amorphous silica and hydrous amorphous silica. *Canadian Journal of Chemistry*. 1956;**34**(10): pp. 1483-96.
- [16] W.J. Malfait, R. Verel, M.M. Koebel. Hydrophobization of Silica Aerogels: Insights from Quantitative Solid-State NMR Spectroscopy. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*. 2014;**118**(44): pp. 25545-54.
- [17] T. Woignier, J. Phalippou. Skeletal density of silica aerogels. *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids*. 1987;**93**(1): pp. 17-21.
- [18] H. Bahramnia, H.M. Semnani, A. Habibolahzadeh, H. Abdoos. The Effect of 3-(Glycidoloxo Propyl) Trimethoxy Silane Concentration on Surface Modification of SiO₂ Nanoparticles. *Silicon*. 2022;**14**(9): pp. 4969-77.
- [19] A.V. Rao, M.M. Kulkarni. Hydrophobic properties of TMOS/TMES-based silica aerogels. *Materials Research Bulletin*. 2002;**37**(9): pp. 1667-77.